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Mechanisms of limitation of oxygen delivery during veno- venous extracorporeal membrane oxygenation

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Abstract:

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Delivery of oxygen to the mitochondrium is process involving multiple steps. We here present the integration of the mechanisms of oxygen delivery during veno- venous extracorporeal membrane oxygenation into a holistic physiological model. The hypothesis derived from this model is, that lowering the cardiac output during V-V ECMO support might increase oxygen delivery to the tissues by improving oxygen diffusion.

Main Manuscript Text

Mechanisms of limitation of oxygen delivery during veno- venous extracorporeal membrane oxygenation

Ensuring adequate tissue oxygenation is a cornerstone of intensive care medicine. We here present a new integration of mechanisms of tissue oxygenation during veno- venous extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (V-V ECMO) into a holistic physiologic model.

An integrated physiological model of tissue oxygenation describes oxygen delivery as process of multiple steps: Diffusion of the oxygen from the alveolus to the pulmonary capillary, convective transport via perfusion with oxygen mostly bound to hemoglobin (Hb), diffusion from capillary through tissue to the mitochondrium. As all steps are in a row, a limitation can occur on each of these steps.¹⁻³

The global convective oxygen delivery (DO₂) can be described by the known formula:

$$DO_2 = CO \times CaO_2$$

where CO is the cardiac output and CaO₂ oxygen content of arterial blood. The main determinants of CaO₂ are hemoglobin concentration (Hb) and arterial oxygen saturation (SaO₂).

Patients with severe respiratory failure may experience a total loss of lung function. In these cases, V-V ECMO may provide the entire oxygen supply for the patients. If the Hb is considered constant, the DO₂ is determined by the ECMO- flow.

In a subset of patients, a high cardiac output (CO) that is significantly higher than the maximal achievable effective ECMO flow, will lead to a significant addition of venous blood, consequently lowering the SaO₂. There is controversy whether the addition of beta- blockers with the intention of lowering the CO and thus increasing the SaO₂ is beneficial, because the total amount of oxygen is not changed.⁴

To introduce the integrated model of tissue oxygenation during V-V ECMO in cases of total lung failure, we analyze two situations (Situation A and B). We consider these situations to be completely equal regarding ECMO flow and all physiologic parameters and to differ only in regard to CO and SaO₂

We make some simplifying assumptions as in the original model by Wagner et al⁵:

1. Situation A : High CO (QA) , low CaO₂ (CaO₂A), DO₂A = QA x CaO₂A; Situation B: Low CO (QB), higher CaO₂ (CaO₂B), DO₂B = QB x CaO₂B and DO₂A = DO₂B
2. PO₂ in the veins draining a certain tissue (PvO₂) is proportional to PO₂ in the capillaries (PcapO₂) with a constant factor k.
3. The oxygen consumption (VO₂) on the convective step of oxygen transport can be described as $VO_2 = Q \times (CaO_2 - CvO_2)$
4. PO₂ at the mitochondrium (PmitO₂) is negligible
5. The VO₂ on the diffusion step of oxygen transport can be described as $VO_2 = D \times (PcapO_2 - PmitO_2) = D \times k \times PvO_2$ with D being the diffusion capacity of a certain tissue
6. The dissolved oxygen is in equilibrium with the hemoglobin bound oxygen following the sigmoid oxygen dissociation curve

With these underlying assumptions we can generate a Wagner- diagram depicting Situation A and B (Figure 1).

The intersections of the diffusion line with the curves of the convective transport are the values for maximal VO₂.

As it can be seen on the diagram, we consider the convective maximal DO_2 to be identical in both situations if PvO_2 would be zero. For any given VO_2 (broken line in Figure 1) the PvO_2 in Situation A will be lower than the PvO_2 in situation B, because the oxygen content in any given volume of blood will be higher in situation B.

If we now introduce the diffusion capacity in our model, we see, that the VO_{2max} on the diffusion step is higher in situation B, because the concentration gradient of O_2 between the capillary and the mitochondrium is higher.

Since a limitation on the diffusion step has been described in past research, we consider it to be an important component of a holistic concept of oxygen delivery into the tissues.

While values for PaO_2 around 55mmHg have been considered safe in past clinical trials (HOT- ICU, ICU-ROX), the LOCO₂ trial was stopped early because of an increased number in mesenterial ischemia⁶⁻⁸.

Our hypothesis is, that in PaO_2 values below the lower threshold in the past trials, a diffusion limitation might lead to tissue hypoxia in patients with low CaO_2 values despite an identical convective DO_2 . Diffusion limitation as the limiting factor of oxygen delivery has previously been described.⁹⁻¹¹ We therefore suggest, that the use of medications to decrease the CO in situations of total lung failure and ECMO support might decrease the risk of tissue hypoxia by accounting for the risk of a limitation of the diffusion.

While a previously discussed mathematical model suggests, that the convective DO_2 is improved in the situation of increased CO and reduced SaO_2 , this does not take into account the following steps of tissue oxygenation⁴. A decrease in CO might worsen perfusion on the microvascular level, so this needs to be balanced against limitations in diffusion. On the other hand, lowering CO will decrease O_2 demand by decreasing cardiac power output. To our knowledge, there is currently no established cut- off for CO and CaO_2 in the context of V-V ECMO to decide when lowering CO and thus increasing diffusion is beneficial.

There are multiple possible options to solve this question, including data- mining of hemodynamic and blood gas data from patients treated with V-V ECMO, mathematical modelling of tissue perfusion and diffusion or models using animal tissue for direct testing.

Figure 1:

Legend to Figure 1: Wagner- diagram of convective transport in situation A (high CO, blue line) and situation B (low CO, red line)

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